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Analysis of the Current Situation of Green Tourism Development in Quang Ninh, Vietnam

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Abstract:

The goal of this article is to analyze the current situation of green tourism development in Quang Ninh, thereby providing development opportunities and challenges for the tourism industry in Quang Ninh province, Vietnam. The article synthesizes secondary data from domestic and international studies and reports, thereby providing analyses of the current development, opportunities and future challenges for Quang Ninh's tourism industry in Vietnam.

Keywords: *Green Tourism, Quang Ninh, Vietnam*

1. Introduction

Quang Ninh, with its rich and diverse natural resources, especially the natural wonder of the world Ha Long Bay, has always been considered one of the leading tourist centers of Vietnam. However, under the pressure of economic development and rapid urbanization, Quang Ninh is facing many challenges in protecting the environment and maintaining sustainability for the tourism industry.

Green tourism – a sustainable tourism model that focuses on environmental protection, efficient use of natural resources and respect for indigenous cultures – is emerging as a global trend. In the context of Vietnam's commitment to achieve net zero emissions by 2050 and promote green growth, the development of green tourism is not only an urgent requirement but also a strategic direction for Quang Ninh.

However, the transition to a green tourism model in Quang Ninh is not an easy task. This locality is having to balance the short-term economic benefits from traditional tourism activities with the requirements of environmental protection and sustainable development. The questions are: How to develop green tourism in Quang Ninh? Is this an opportunity to improve the tourism status of the locality or just a major challenge to economic and environmental development?

With the above issues, the study on "Green tourism development in Quang Ninh: Opportunities or challenges?" aims to analyze the current situation, identify opportunities and challenges, and propose appropriate solutions to develop a green tourism model, contributing to improving the quality of sustainable development for the local tourism industry.

2. Literature review

Green Tourism

"Green tourism" is the development of tourism based on the rational and efficient exploitation of resources and resources; promote the development of green tourism products and services for consumption; associated with the preservation and promotion of natural resource values and national cultural heritage; protecting the

environment, preserving biodiversity, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adapting to climate change". Therefore, green tourism is a responsible way of doing tourism, helping to effectively implement the goals of sustainable tourism development.

In Vietnam, the development of green tourism has been oriented in the guidelines, guidelines and policies of the Party and the laws of the State. As early as 2014, the Prime Minister issued the National Action Plan on green growth for the period 2014-2020.

The Prime Minister's Decision No. 147/QĐ-TTg promulgating Vietnam's Tourism Development Strategy to 2030 has the view: "Develop sustainable and inclusive tourism, on the basis of green growth, maximize the contribution of tourism to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals; effectively manage and use natural resources, protect the environment and biodiversity, proactively adapt to climate change, ensure national defense and security".

In the Prime Minister's Decision No. 882/QĐ-TTg promulgating the National Action Plan on green growth for the 2021-2030 period, the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism is assigned to preside over two groups of tasks: "Improving institutions and policies for management and development of tourism in the direction of green and sustainable growth" and "Prioritizing the development of all types of tourism in the direction of green growth (eco-tourism, community tourism, agricultural and rural tourism, island resort tourism associated with blue sea economic development, adventure sports tourism to ensure green standards and criteria...), development of green tourism products".

And most recently, on May 18, 2023, the Government issued Resolution 82/NQ-CP on the main tasks and solutions to accelerate recovery and accelerate effective and sustainable tourism development, the Government assigned the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism to develop and implement the Green Tourism Action Program for the period of 2023 – 2025, protect the natural and social environment at key tourist destinations in the orientation of "Green, clean, beautiful, civilized and friendly tourist destinations".

All mark a positive step in forming a green tourism trend in Vietnam, bringing benefits to the environment and human health, and helping the tourism industry develop in a sustainable direction, creating better and deeper experiences for both tourists and destinations.

Sustainable green tourism model

Green tourism is not only a new concept but has become a sustainable development trend in the global tourism industry, in which its diverse forms are increasingly popular with tourists. Current green tourism models not only focus on environmental protection but also aim to raise community awareness, create sustainable economic benefits and preserve local cultural values.

Green tourism combines sports and health training

This type meets the needs of the modern traveler who wants to combine the travel experience with improved health and wellness. Popular activities include hiking, cycling, yoga at natural areas such as forests, mountains, or beaches. These trips not only bring health benefits but also contribute to raising awareness of the value of natural resources. For example, eco-tourism areas that organize meditation or yoga sessions in green areas are receiving a strong response from international visitors.

Limited or non-plastic travel

Plastic waste is a major problem for the global environment, especially in tourist destinations. Many green tourism areas have committed to eliminating or minimizing single-use plastics. Instead, they encourage visitors to bring their own water bottles, use cloth bags, and take advantage of recycled products. Green hotels also eliminate single-use plastic bottles in their rooms, replacing them with glass bottles or eco-friendly water supply equipment.

Use environmentally friendly means of transport

Transportation plays an important role in reducing carbon emissions from the tourism industry. Green tourism models encourage the use of public transportation such as buses, trains, or trams instead of private cars. In addition, bicycles and electric scooters are becoming popular choices in tourist destinations. Cities such as Hoi An, Da Lat and Hue in Vietnam have adopted green transport initiatives, making it easy for tourists to access environmentally friendly vehicles.

Participate in garbage cleanup and environmental protection activities

Green tourism is not only about enjoyment but also encouraging tourists to participate in environmental protection activities at the destination. These activities include cleaning up trash on beaches, collecting trash in the forest, or participating in cleanup campaigns at nature reserves. Programs such as "Clean the Beach" at beaches in Vietnam or "Trash Hero" have attracted many international tourists to participate, contributing to raising community awareness and creating positive social values.

Choosing a green place to live

Green accommodations are becoming more and more popular, with designs close to nature, using environmentally friendly materials and saving energy. Green resorts, homestays and hotels are often built with open spaces, planted with many trees, using solar energy or water recycling systems. These places not only provide a comfortable experience, but also provide an opportunity for visitors to understand and support environmental protection initiatives.

3. The development of green tourism in Quang Ninh

Resolution No. 07-NQ/TU (dated 24/5/2013) of the Provincial Party Committee on Quang Ninh tourism development in the 2013-2020 period, with a vision to 2030, determines: Developing the province's tourism in the direction of sustainability, professionalism, modernity, efficiency, focus and focus, so that tourism becomes a key economic sector and accounts for an increasing proportion in the province's GDP structure; making an important contribution to implementing 3 strategic breakthroughs, associated with the growth model, restructuring the economy, transforming the development mode from "brown" to "green".

Concretizing the resolution, the province has persistently and consistently implemented the policy of sustainable and inclusive tourism development, on the basis of green growth, which is a requirement throughout policies, strategies and planning. Accordingly, the tourism industry has maximized the available potential, creating unique tourism products; associating tourism development with the preservation and promotion of national cultural values and identities; manage and exploit sustainably, effectively use natural resources, protect the environment, and conserve biodiversity.

Typical are the models: Agricultural tourism, community tourism, ecology in Binh Lieu, Hai Ha, Tien Yen, Mong Cai; Boating tourism service cooperative takes tourists to visit fishing villages, Ky Thuong Am Vap farm community tourist area (Khe Phuong village, Ky Thuong commune, Ha Long city); community tourism in Yen Duc village (Dong Trieu Town) of Indochina Cruise Joint Stock Company... has brought many interesting experiences to visitors; contributing to promoting cultural values, creating jobs, and reducing poverty sustainably for the locality.

According to the trend of green tourism, environmental issues are also of special concern to Quang Ninh. Accordingly, the province actively works and receives support from JICA (Japan International Cooperation Agency) in the project to promote green growth in the Ha Long Bay area and has achieved certain results. In particular, it must be mentioned the development of green sail criteria for cruise ships on Ha Long Bay; develop energy-saving solutions; published a white paper on green growth in Ha Long Bay... In addition, proactively apply advanced technology such as oil and water separation techniques to filter wastewater before releasing it

into the environment, do not dump waste directly into the bay, use all glass water bottles, paper straws, paper cups, etc. to minimize harm to the environment during the operation of cruise ships in the bay.

Not only in Ha Long Bay, over the past time, Co To island district has also built a sustainable green tourism environment. According to Mr. Nguyen Hai Linh, Head of the Department of Culture, Sports and Tourism of Co To district, from September 1, 2022, the district People's Committee has piloted the regulation that tourists do not bring plastic bottles, plastic bags, and materials that are at risk of causing environmental pollution to the island. After 1 year of effective pilot implementation, from September 15, 2023, the district will apply a pilot implementation to make it mandatory for all tourists not to bring plastic bags and single-use plastic items to the island. In addition, all administrative agencies, schools, markets, service businesses, and fishing vessels in Co To are also not allowed to use plastic bags, disposable plastics and materials that are at risk of polluting the marine environment.

In order to implement this regulation, the District People's Committee has requested the Department of Transport, Quang Ninh Inland Waterway Port Authority, and the Inland Waterway Port Authority in Van Don - Co To to coordinate in propagating to passenger and cargo shipping lines to Co To; inspect and require vehicle owners and passengers not to bring plastic bags and disposable plastic waste to Co To Island; consider issuing an exit order only when shipping lines ensure the above provisions.

4. Opportunities and challenges in developing green tourism in Quang Ninh

Chance

Favorable geographical location and climate

Quang Ninh is blessed with a prime location on the shore of the Gulf of Tonkin, which is a gateway for economic and cultural exchanges with the Northern provinces as well as neighboring countries. With a coastline of more than 250 km, Quang Ninh owns many beautiful beaches, large and small islands, along with a mild and cool climate.

In particular, Ha Long Bay – one of the seven new natural wonders of the world recognized by UNESCO – is a prominent highlight in the green tourism development strategy. Activities such as kayaking, exploring caves, or seeing the magnificent landscapes here not only attract tourists but also promote environmental awareness. The geographical and climatic advantages make Quang Ninh an ideal destination for tourists in their journey to discover nature-friendly forms of tourism.

Rich ecosystem

Quang Ninh stands out for its rich biodiversity and ecosystem, including:

Bai Tu Long National Forest: A place to preserve many rare species of flora and fauna, as well as an ideal area for eco-tours combined with environmental protection. Mangroves and coral reefs: These areas not only have high ecological value but also support the development of tourism activities, research and environmental education. Co To Island: A famous landmark with its pristine beauty, it is an ideal destination for nature exploration tours.

With these advantages, Quang Ninh can deploy many types of tourism such as ecotourism, research tourism, and tourism combined with conservation, helping to protect natural resources and create sustainable revenue for the locality.

Cultural diversity

Quang Ninh is home to many ethnic minorities such as the Dao, San Diu, and Tay, creating a diverse and rich culture. Traditional festivals such as the Tra Co communal festival, Cua Ong festival or the unique customs and customs of the Dao ethnic people in the mountainous areas of Quang Ninh attract great attention from tourists.

In addition, traditional handicraft villages such as Vung Vieng fishing village or Dong Trieu pottery village are also important highlights in the green tourism journey. These experiences not only help visitors better understand the local culture but also encourage the preservation and sustainable development of local cultural values.

Support policies from the government

The government of Quang Ninh province has had many positive policies to promote the development of green tourism, including:

Infrastructure investment: Develop transport routes connecting tourist attractions, and at the same time focus on building accommodation facilities that meet green standards. **Supporting environmental protection projects:** Creating conditions for businesses and organizations to implement nature conservation programs, minimizing environmental impacts from tourism activities.

Promote green tourism: Organize seminars and exhibitions to raise awareness of the benefits of green tourism for the community and local economy. These policies have been creating a favorable environment for businesses, organizations and people to participate in the development of green tourism, contributing to improving the quality of life and protecting natural resources for future generations.

Challenge

Pressure from the increase in tourists

With the rapid development of the tourism industry, Quang Ninh is facing overcrowding in many tourist destinations, especially in Ha Long Bay – a world natural heritage. The sharp increase in the number of tourists during the peak season leads to negative impacts on the environment, including:

Environmental pollution: The amount of waste from visitors, especially in areas with high foot traffic such as beaches, islands, or during visits to natural monuments, can lead to serious environmental pollution. Without effective control measures, this situation can have a long-term impact on the landscape and habitat of animals and plants in the area. **Impact on sensitive ecosystems:** Overcrowding can increase the risk of devastating marine ecosystems and mangroves, two important elements of ecotourism. Activities such as kayaking, cave visits, or resource extraction activities for tourism can all have a direct impact on the sustainability of the ecosystem.

To minimize pressure from tourists, Quang Ninh needs to implement measures to control and allocate tourists reasonably, invest in sustainable infrastructure, and encourage tourists to participate in environmental protection activities.

Awareness of environmental protection of tourists and local communities

Although there have been many campaigns to raise awareness about environmental protection, indiscriminate littering at tourist destinations still exists. Some of the key issues include:

Tourists lack awareness: A part of tourists are not fully aware of the impact of their actions on the environment, such as littering, polluting tourist areas, especially in natural or untapped tourist sites. This threatens the cleanliness of destinations and can degrade the sustainable tourism value of Quang Ninh.

Local communities are not yet aware of environmental protection: While green tourism is a sustainable development model, a part of the local population still does not have enough understanding and interest in environmental protection. Unsustainable use of natural resources, such as overexploitation of natural resources, can reduce the effectiveness of ecotourism strategies.

Therefore, Quang Ninh needs to continue to implement strategies to educate the community and tourists about environmental protection, and at the same time encourage the active participation of people in natural resource protection activities.

Lack of strict management

Although ecotourism has been identified as a strategic sector of Quang Ninh, some tourism infrastructure development projects still do not strictly comply with environmental protection standards. Specific issues that may be encountered include:

Uncontrolled construction: Some tourism constructions such as resorts, resorts, or transport infrastructure may not meet environmental factors, such as affecting natural landscapes, destroying primary forests, etc or change the flow of rivers and streams in the area. **Ineffective tourism management:** Shortcomings in the management, inspection and supervision of tourism activities can lead to business establishments abusing resources, unreasonable exploitation, or not complying with regulations on environmental protection, leading to negative impacts on the local ecosystem and landscape.

Quang Ninh needs to develop and enforce stricter regulations on environmental protection and quality control of tourism development projects, and strengthen the monitoring and assessment of environmental impacts from tourism activities.

Local resources have not been optimized

One of the major challenges to green tourism in Quang Ninh is the lack of training and support for the local community. Many locals are still not fully equipped with knowledge and skills to participate in green tourism activities, leading to ineffective exploitation of local tourism potential.

Lack of community training: Many people do not fully understand the benefits of sustainable tourism development and green tourism. Therefore, their participation in activities such as environmental protection, provision of ecotourism services, or development of tourism products associated with nature is limited.

Lack of formal support: Support policies from local governments are inadequate, leading to the inability of communities to effectively participate in the green tourism value chain. The lack of training, technical and financial support programs can reduce the ability of communities to exploit green tourism opportunities.

5. Solution-oriented

5.1. Green thinking and planning – The foundation for sustainable transformation

In order for green tourism to truly become a sustainable direction, it is necessary to start from a change in the mindset of stakeholders. Green culture is not just a slogan but must be applied to practical actions, from changing personal lifestyles, behaving in the community to building development strategies of businesses and governments. Educational programs, seminars and communication campaigns should be implemented to raise awareness among residents and tourists about the importance of green tourism, thereby encouraging environmentally friendly behavior.

Green planning is the foundation for all steps of sustainable development. Localities need to include environmental protection and natural resources in tourism planning, especially in sensitive areas such as national parks and marine protected areas. The construction of infrastructure with low environmental impact, effective waste and wastewater management should be prioritized. At the same time, it is necessary to integrate the goal of greening tourism into the national strategy, implement action programs such as the National Strategy for Green Growth 2021-2030, and ensure sustainable and long-term tourism development.

Green tourism products, such as ecotourism, community tourism and zero-waste tourism, need to be developed to create experiences that are close to nature and respect local culture. Promulgating a set of national criteria for

green tourism, in line with international standards and actual conditions of Vietnam, will be a guideline for the tourism industry towards sustainable development.

5.2. Technology, community and international cooperation – Promoting green tourism transformation

Technology plays an important role in minimizing environmental impacts and improving the efficiency of tourism management. Measures such as waste treatment, energy saving, and green transportation development need to be promoted. Electric cars, bicycles and clean energy vehicles need to become popular choices for travelers. At the same time, digital technology can support more effective destination management, helping to monitor and evaluate green activities in the tourism industry.

Green tourism needs to be based on the active participation of the local community. People are not only beneficiaries but also active participants in the construction, development and protection of tourist destinations. Community-based tourism models should be encouraged, thereby ensuring direct economic benefits to local people, while raising awareness about the conservation of natural and cultural resources.

In addition, Vietnam needs to strengthen cooperation with international organizations such as UNDP and JICA to receive technical and financial support in the green transition. At the same time, the State needs to have preferential mechanisms to encourage businesses to invest in green tourism projects, from tax exemption and reduction to financial and technical support.

At the same time, it is also necessary to strengthen destination management and environmental conservation. Sustainable destination management requires the synchronous participation of local governments, communities and businesses. Initiatives such as reducing plastic waste, protecting biodiversity and promoting effective waste management need to be strongly implemented in destinations. Moreover, coordination between the parties will help the voices of the local community to be heard, thereby providing appropriate management solutions.

By combining green thinking with technology, community support, and international cooperation, Vietnam's tourism industry will achieve its sustainable development goals and increase its competitiveness in the global market.

6. Conclusion

Green tourism in Quang Ninh has outstanding development potential thanks to favorable factors such as ideal geographical location, rich ecosystem and cultural diversity. These potentials open up great opportunities for the province to develop a sustainable tourism model that not only helps protect the environment but also boosts the local economy and improves the quality of life of the community.

Quang Ninh can take advantage of natural resources such as Ha Long Bay, Bai Tu Long National Forest and Co To islands to develop ecotourism. The provincial government has been aware of the importance of green tourism and has made significant strides in supporting sustainable infrastructure, protecting nature and developing environmentally friendly tourism products. In particular, Quang Ninh's cultural diversity with traditional festivals and traditional crafts will be an important factor in attracting visitors, creating unique and profound experiences.

However, to make these opportunities a reality, Quang Ninh also faces many challenges. The rapid increase in the number of tourists can put great pressure on the environment, leading to pollution and destruction of the ecosystem if not effectively controlled. In addition, the awareness of environmental protection of a part of tourists and local communities is still limited, and the management of tourism development projects is not strict enough, which can cause negative impacts on landscapes and natural resources.

Although there are still many challenges, with determination and supportive policies from the provincial government, Quang Ninh can fully develop green tourism in a sustainable direction. This requires close coordination between authorities, businesses and local communities, in which raising awareness of

environmental protection and developing scientific and sustainable tourism management strategies are decisive factors. If these problems are solved, Quang Ninh will become a bright spot in the green tourism model in Vietnam, creating long-term benefits for both the community and the environment.

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